

Policy Briefing

Revisiting the EU Plastics Strategy

Summary

This briefing argues that the 2018 EU Plastics Strategy needs revision to take into account the wide range of developments that have happened over the last six years. A revised Strategy is needed to help guide policies concerning plastics (including bioplastic). We recommend that the Strategy is reviewed and revised at the same time as the evaluation of the Single Use Plastics Directive (due in July 2027). Such a revision will also need to take account of the provisions of the forthcoming UN Plastics Treaty and the obligations that it will impose on the EU.

Specifically, we recommend that the revision of the Plastics Strategy includes:

- A vision for the future role of plastic in Europe – what plastics (and what types of plastic) are needed for what purposes and what should be substituted for other materials. This will provide a clear understanding of what plastic and plastic waste needs to be managed.
- A clear vision for how full circularity of plastic is to be achieved, in particular the limitations and roles of mechanical and chemical recycling. With this, business and policy can evolve to deliver this future.
- A consistent approach to expectations for different types of plastics, including on whether they might cause harm and with regard to reuse and recycling.
- A consistent approach concerning the correct use and waste management of new sustainable plastics such as bioplastics and biopolymers. These have different uses for different market applications and it is necessary to guide its correct uses.

Introduction

The EU Plastics Strategy [1] is now six years old. At the time of its development, it was a major policy step forward. It was produced in reaction to the serious plastic pollution problems being reported and recognising that Europe needed to think differently about plastic waste following the effective ban on shipment of plastic waste to China. This coincided with evolving thinking about the circular economy, wherein plastics are a key material of focus.

A major legislative consequence of the Plastics Strategy was the Directive on single use plastics [2]. Since then, there has been the policy on bio-based, biodegradable and compostable plastics [3] and the proposal on packaging and packaging waste [4], together with further development of the circular economy policy [5] and the Commission Regulation restricting intentionally added microplastics [6].

While the EU Plastics Strategy was a major advance at the time, today it no longer provides a sufficient strategic approach to guide Europe's trajectory concerning plastics. It does not set out a vision for what we need plastic for (and also what we may need different plastics, such as bioplastics, for). It does not describe what is a realistic circular plastics economy for Europe (e.g. are

there limits to recycling?). Answering these questions would enable us to determine what plastics we want and do not want and what technologies we need (e.g. for recycling). Furthermore, a Plastics Treaty is being negotiated at UN level which the EU will need to adopt and there are important elements likely to be included that the Plastics Strategy does not have.

We, therefore, recommend that the EU Plastics Strategy is revised. This briefing explores some of the issues a revised Strategy should address and also the timing of a revision.

SEALIVE

This briefing is produced by the SEALIVE H2020 project, funded by the European Union (EU). SEALIVE aims to demonstrate innovative circular strategies for bio-based plastics in land and sea applications. The project also aims to stand as a reference to be disseminated and widely used in Europe and beyond. To do this, SEALIVE will implement sustainable solutions based on novel bio-based plastics to avoid plastics ending-up on land and sea. As part of the work of SEALIVE, there is particular research on the policy implications of the production and use of bio-based, biodegradable and compostable plastics, analysing policies and developing conclusions and recommendations for future policy development. This briefing is an output of this research within SEALIVE.

The EU Plastics Strategy

The Strategy provides a summary of the key problems of plastics in society – increasing production, problems of disposal, littering, microplastics, challenges of recycling, etc. To address these problems, it sets out a vision for Europe’s new plastics economy, and explores this around the following areas:

- Improved recycling of plastics.
- Tackling littering.
- Establishing a regulatory framework for biodegradable plastics.
- The problems of microplastics.
- Innovation to deliver objectives.
- Global actions.

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Some of the key developments needed to achieve the objectives of the Strategy are highlighted in the Strategy:

- Improved design for greater durability, reuse and high-quality recycling.
- Separate collection of plastic waste reaches very high levels. Recycling of plastic packaging waste achieves levels comparable with those of other packaging materials.
- EU plastics recycling capacity is significantly extended and modernised.
- Recycled plastics have become an increasingly valuable feedstock for industries.
- The market for recycled and innovative plastics is successfully established. The plastics value chain is far more integrated. Substances hampering recycling processes have been replaced or phased out.
- Innovative materials and alternative feedstocks for plastic production are used where they are more sustainable for specific market applications.
- Innovative materials could meet packaging requirements with adequate formulation and could be organically recycled and reused for some applications, as well as separated to avoid contamination of waste streams.
- Plastic waste generation is decoupled from growth.
- The leakage of plastics into the environment decreases drastically.

The Strategy contains few numerical targets, but its most important is that, by 2030, more than half of plastic waste generated in Europe is recycled. We know now that this will not be met. Current recycling rates are too low to change this much in the next six years. The Strategy correctly highlights the prerequisites for a circular plastics economy – proper separation of plastic waste, the right recycling technologies and value chains which mean that there is an economic basis for such a circular economy. Unfortunately, these preconditions are not being met. In 2023 the price of recycled plastic dropped significantly, and EU policy is not providing clarity on the technological systems needed. Indeed, these problems continue in 2024 and there are concerns over the relative pricing of recycled plastic, including against cheap imports of virgin plastic from outside of the EU.

The EU Plastics Strategy provided a good diagnosis of the plastics problem. It also recognised that addressing this problem requires a holistic approach across many areas. However, its proposed actions effectively were to move forward from the current situation. These were important steps, but the Strategy did not describe an end point (or end points). This is needed to ensure policies take us in the right direction and concretely deliver on expected results, rather than merely resulting in moderate improvement.

The need for a clear vision of the role of plastics

The Plastics Strategy begins by stating that “Plastic is an important and ubiquitous material in our economy and daily lives”. It later proceeds to set out what it calls “A vision for Europe’s new plastics economy”. However, while it sets out actions relevant to improving circularity of plastics and reducing their environmental impacts, it does not set out a **vision** for plastics in the European economy. This is forgivable for a policy published in January 2018, but this now needs to be rectified.

Actions to reduce some plastics (single use) have been taken (though there are issues with some substitutes). There is action to improve design for recycling. There are new targets coming for recycling of plastic packaging and use of recycled content in packaging. All of these are important steps forward. However, they are steps being taken without the context of a final “destination”.

Plastic waste is a problem, but plastic plays many key functions in society. A Plastics Strategy should set out what should the future role of plastics in Europe be – what functions are appropriate for plastic and what for alternative materials? Once we have decided what we want plastic for, we can then look at what types of plastic are best for those functions, and which are consistent with a circular economy. It is then possible to estimate future plastic production, types of plastic and end of life management. Of course, these would be estimates and would evolve, but it would set a clear context. For example, if some essential uses of plastics are not recycled at end of life, then it is important to focus on solutions to this.

The need to describe a circular plastics economy

Given the discussion in the Plastics Strategy on recycling of plastics and the explicit context of the EU’s Circular Economy policy, it is perhaps surprising that the Strategy does not set out a vision for a circular economy for plastic. Clearly reduction, reuse and recycling are essential to a circular plastic economy, but repeating these principles only gets us so far. To make practical and policy decisions we need to know what a fully circular plastics economy would look like. What would this mean for the different types of plastics and their end-of-life management to deliver circularity?

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An important source for thinking about a plastics circular economy is the Ellen MacArthur Foundation [8]. The key elements it sets out for this are:

- Elimination of problematic or unnecessary plastic packaging through redesign, innovation, and new delivery models is a priority.
- Reuse models to be applied where relevant, reducing the need for single-use packaging.
- All plastic packaging to be 100% reusable, recyclable, or compostable.
- All plastic packaging to be reused, recycled, or composted in practice.
- The use of plastic to be fully decoupled from the consumption of finite resources.
- All plastic packaging to be free of hazardous chemicals, and the health, safety, and rights of all people involved are respected.

These points are all good, but EMF focuses its efforts on design for reuse and recycling. The statement that “all plastic packaging is reused, recycled, or composted in practice” is a statement of circularity, but we do not have detail about how this is to be done. This is also lacking in the EU Plastics Strategy. On a wider point, some of these objectives may be more widely applicable, e.g. addressing all packaging and not only that which is made of plastic.

Ultimately the question comes down to whether the current waste management systems (collection, sorting and recycling) are the correct systems for a circular plastics economy. Most recycling of plastics is done using different mechanical recycling systems. These have limitations on their ability to cope with contamination, different plastic mixtures, ability of consumers to separate materials, etc [9]. There are problems with the deterioration of the quality of recyclates over time, some of which can be managed in product design, better sorting and recycling processes. However, with repeated recycling quality declines. For example, mixed colours mean that the recycled product eventually becomes grey and becomes limited in use. A further important issue is that not all recycled plastics are approved for food and/or cosmetic applications, leading to a lack of availability of mechanical recycled plastics for these markets.

A further problem for mechanical recycling in the circular plastics economy is the economics of recycling. Most polymers can be separated using optical sorting technology (including different types of bio-based plastics explored in SEALIVE). However, separation of many different polymers requires the circulation of a waste stream through a sorter several times, increasing costs considerably. There are even greater challenges with laminates. Further, even if the polymers are separated, is there a market to justify the costs of recycling? These value chain problems are significant.

The alternative is chemical recycling, where the polymers are broken down to the molecular level and new polymers from this can be manufactured [10]. Chemical recycling requires more energy use and there is concern about its ability to cope with contaminants. However, it can cope with a wide range of different homogenous polymers for which value chains are lacking through the mechanical recycling route.

Essentially, much plastic may go through several cycles of mechanically recycling and then be subject to final disposal (e.g. energy from waste). Therefore, ultimately, plastic moving through this system is not in a circular economy, but a linear economy. It is simply a much slower linear economy than a make, use and dispose economy. It is a more efficient linear economy, but not circular in the end. This is why a proper vision for what plastics circularity looks like is important. Biodegradable polymers can also be mechanically and chemically recycled, but additionally organically recycled, making it a true circular process. So, these innovative materials should be investigated and promoted in applications where it makes sense.

For example, the 2022 proposal on packaging and packaging waste sets a target of 50% recycling of plastic packaging and (for 2040) that the plastic recycled content of packaging should be between 50 and 65%, depending on the packaging. This is consistent with the limitations of mechanical recycling – good collection and recycling could meet the 50% target. However, this is still not expected to go through many cycles before disposal and not for all plastic types and uses (e.g. food contact use). Ultimately, the targets can be viewed as a vision of a very efficient linear plastics economy.

We have not explored the relative merits of mechanical and chemical recycling (including future technical and economic opportunities and limitations). However, we have identified that the EU Plastics Strategy does need to set out its view of the appropriate recycling approaches to deliver a circular plastics economy in Europe. It is clear from the 2022 proposal on packaging and packaging waste that the Commission views future plastics recycling as an incremental improvement on the current approaches (hence the limits on total quantities of plastic recycled and concern over contamination of biodegradable plastics in plastics recycling). We consider that a circular plastics economy in Europe should have a more ambitious vision.

The EU Plastics Strategy instead should describe a recycling system for plastics consistent with a vision for a full circular plastics economy. What should be the relative roles of mechanical and chemical recycling to maximise recycling of as many polymers as possible and as much plastic waste as possible? With that in place, it is possible to define more sustainable targets for packaging, make better policy for biodegradable and compostable plastics, etc. It will also avoid the waste industry investing in recycling facilities that might deliver the immediate targets, but are not sufficient for a maximised circular plastics economy.

We, therefore, recommend that a revised EU Plastics Strategy sets out a clear vision for what plastics will be needed in the future, the waste management systems to maximise circularity for these plastics, and the economic foundations necessary to deliver circularity.

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A consistent approach for all plastics, including bio-based and biodegradable plastics

The Plastics Strategy recognises the growing importance of bio-based and biodegradable plastics. However, its conclusions have since been overtaken by the 2022 Commission policy on bio-based, biodegradable and compostable plastics [11]. The policy contains many aspects which we cannot go into here. However, it does contain a statement which is highly relevant to a future revised Plastics Strategy. It states, “the use of plastics that biodegrade in the open environment must be limited to materials for which full bio-degradability has proven to be below a specific and evidence-based timeframe to avoid environmental harm, and to specific applications where consumption reduction or reuse are not viable options and where the full removal, collection and recycling of plastic products is not feasible.”

Essentially the policy states that use of biodegradable plastics must not cause harm [12] and should be limited to where alternatives allowing reuse, recycling, etc., are not viable. These are good objectives for plastics in general. We do not want plastics that cause harm and we want recycling of plastics. However, most plastics in the open environment will (or have the potential to) cause harm and most plastics used are not currently reused or recycled.

The Commission policy, therefore, places expectations on biodegradable plastics that are not applied to any other plastics. It may be reasonable for different types of plastic to be subject to different expectations. But this should be stated explicitly (and justified) in the Plastics Strategy. To what plastics should “no harm” expectations be applied and to what plastics are reuse and recycling expectations to be applied? A limited expectation for biodegradable plastics alone is not appropriate. It risks avoiding opportunities where biodegradable plastics may reduce harm.

We, therefore, recommend that expectations for different plastics regarding their potential to cause harm to the environment and to be reused and recycled should be included in a revised Plastics Strategy. All could have different and specific end of life to guarantee a correct waste management and the best option to avoid plastic waste contamination.

The UN Plastics Treaty

This briefing is arguing for a revision of EU policy. However, this cannot be undertaken in isolation from developments at United Nations (UN) level. At the time of writing, a UN Plastics Treaty is being negotiated. On 4 September 2023, the United Nations Environment Programme published a Zero draft text of the Treaty [13]. This was discussed at the Intergovernmental Negotiating Committee to develop this instrument in Nairobi on 13–19 November 2023 and since then an advanced version of the revised zero draft (UNEP/PP/INC.4/3) [14] has been published.

Clearly, this is a rapidly developing area of policy and we do not propose to go into detail here. Indeed, SEALIVE has produced a separate briefing on the Treaty [15]. The two points of relevance to this briefing and revision of the Plastics Strategy are, firstly, that the Treaty is relatively comprehensive in its approach to plastics. It also (at this stage) includes possible provisions for parties to reduce production or reduce demand for plastics. These are not yet aspects of EU policy as such. Whatever the final detail of the Treaty, it will be necessary to re-examine EU policy to determine if it is fit for purpose to implement the Treaty in the EU.

Second, the draft Treaty would require Parties to develop national programmes to deliver its objectives. It contains a range of alternative approaches and issues to analyse, so that much needs to be developed by the Parties. For the EU, a revised Plastics Strategy would seem an ideal vehicle to present a plan for the EU on how it will implement the Treaty.

Timing

As already noted, a review of the Plastics Strategy should take place after adoption of the UN Plastics Treaty. There is, however, another important date and that concerns the requirement on the European Commission to review the Single Use Plastics Directive (SUPD). Article 15 requires this evaluation to be completed by 3 July 2027, which means considerable work prior to this date.

As well as evaluating issues specific to the Directive (e.g. which items are banned), Article 15 includes two further relevant aspects to review. The first is to assess changes in materials used, consumption patterns, business models and alternatives, all in the context of a life cycle assessment. This links to issues that need to be analysed for the wider Plastics Strategy.

A further aspect that the evaluation must consider is “an assessment of the scientific and technical progress concerning criteria or a standard for biodegradability in the marine environment applicable to single-use plastic products within the scope of this Directive and their single-use substitutes which [decompose quickly enough] to be harmful to marine life and not to lead to an accumulation of plastics in the environment”. This clearly should draw upon the results from the SEALIVE project and other research funded under Horizon 2020 and other programmes. Importantly, the evaluation should compare biodegradable plastic products with substitutes for plastic and should ensure that the ultimate criterion for assessment is harm. Again, while this is an important aspect of the review of the SUPD, this type of analysis has wider implications for the Plastics Strategy than the issues addressed by the SUPD.

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Conclusions and recommendations for the EU Plastics Strategy

It is essential that the EU has a clear, comprehensive strategy on plastics which establishes the expectations on plastics in a circular economy. It can then form the basis for further law and policy development in specific areas. The EU Plastics Strategy recognises this. However, it has limitations which need to be addressed, drawing on research and policy developments in the more than five years since it was adopted.

In particular, it is recommended that the Plastics Strategy is revised and addresses four fundamental gaps:

- A vision for the future role of plastic in Europe – what plastic (and what types of plastic) are needed for what purposes and what should be substituted for other materials. This will provide a clear understanding of what plastic and plastic waste needs to be managed.
- A clear vision for how full circularity of plastic is to be achieved, in particular the limitations and roles of mechanical and chemical recycling. With this, business and policy can evolve to deliver this future.
- A consistent approach to expectations for different types of plastics, including on whether they might cause harm and with regard to reuse and recycling.
- A consistent approach concerning the correct use and waste management of new sustainable plastics such as bioplastics and biopolymers. These have different uses for different market applications and it is necessary to guide its correct uses.

¹ A European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy 16.1.2018 COM(2018) 28. <https://ec.europa.eu/environment/circular-economy/pdf/plastics-strategy.pdf>

² Directive (EU) 2019/904 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment.

³ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/publications/communication-eu-policy-framework-biobased-biodegradable-and-compostable-plastics_en

⁴ European Commission 2022b. Proposal for a revision of EU legislation on Packaging and Packaging Waste. COM(2022) 677. 30.11.2022. https://environment.ec.europa.eu/publications/proposal-packaging-and-packaging-waste_en

⁵ European Commission (2020). COM(2020) 98 final. A new Circular Economy Action Plan – for a cleaner and more competitive Europe. Brussels, Belgium.

⁶ Commission Regulation (EU) 2023/2055 - Restriction of microplastics intentionally added to products - European Commission. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32023R2055>

⁷ Plastics Recyclers Europe 12 October 2023. <https://www.plasticsrecyclers.eu/news/low-demand-and-high-imports-endanger-the-european-plastics-recycling-industry/#:~:text=Plastics%20recycling%20market%20in%20Europe,the%20EU%20have%20signifi,cantly%20increased>

⁸ Ellen MacArthur Foundation Our vision for a circular economy for plastics. <https://ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/plastics-vision>

- ⁹ Schyns, Z. O. G. and Shaver, M. P. 2020. Mechanical Recycling of Packaging Plastics: A Review Macro Molecular Rapid Communications. <https://doi.org/10.1002/marc.202000415>
- ¹⁰ OMV Group. The right recycling method for all plastics. <https://www.omv.com/en/blog/the-right-recycling-method-for-all-plastics>
- ¹¹ COM(2022)682, 30.11.2022. https://environment.ec.europa.eu/publications/communication-eu-policy-framework-biobased-biodegradable-and-compostable-plastics_en
- ¹² Note that the potential to cause harm is not just a feature of the type of plastic, but also of the type of product (e.g. a plastic bag compared to a block of plastic).
- ¹³ <https://wedocs.unep.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.11822/43239/ZERODRAFT.pdf>
- ¹⁴ <https://wedocs.unep.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.11822/44526/RevisedZeroDraftText.pdf>
- ¹⁵ Policy Briefing: Zero Draft Text of the International Legally Binding Instrument on Plastic Pollution, Including in the Marine Environment: Farmer, Andrew; Orthodoxou, Demetra; Baldwin, Christina. 20 October 2023. 10.5281/zenodo.10027313

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